

Percutaneous Catheter Drainage of the Liver Abscess: The Most Effective Minimally Invasive Method

Kumar Abhishek Ranjan¹, Amit Kumar², Pranava Dutta Verma³

¹Senior Resident, Department of General Surgery, Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

²Senior Resident, Department of General Surgery, Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

³Professor, Department of General surgery, Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 5-04-2024 / Revised: 15-05-2024 / Accepted: 10-06-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Pranava Dutta Verma

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Liver abscess are serious infections within the liver that can lead to severe complications and high mortality if not managed effectively. Traditional management involves antimicrobial therapy combined with surgical drainage, but recent advancements have favoured minimally invasive techniques like percutaneous catheter drainage (PCD) and percutaneous needle aspiration (PNA).

Aim: This study aims to evaluate the efficacy and safety of percutaneous catheter drainage compared to conventional treatment methods in the management of liver abscess.

Methods: A prospective cohort study was conducted with 87 participants diagnosed with liver abscess. Participants were divided into two groups: the PCD group (n=43) and the control group (n=44). Data on demographic characteristics, clinical outcomes, complication rates, and recurrence rates were collected and analyzed. Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 23.0, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: The PCD group demonstrated a significantly higher abscess resolution rate of 90.7% compared to 75% in the control group ($p=0.04$). The mean time to resolution was significantly shorter in the PCD group (9.8 days) compared to the control group (14.6 days) ($p < 0.001$). Additionally, the PCD group experienced a shorter hospital stay (7.5 days vs. 11.8 days, $p < 0.001$) and a lower overall complication rate (11.6% vs. 25%, $p=0.12$). Recurrence rates were also lower in the PCD group (7% vs. 13.6%, $p=0.49$).

Conclusion: Percutaneous catheter drainage is an effective and safe minimally invasive procedure for managing liver abscess. It offers superior clinical outcomes, including higher resolution rates, shorter hospital stays, and potentially lower complication and recurrence rates compared to conventional treatment methods.

Recommendations: PCD should be considered the preferred treatment option for liver abscess especially in settings where resources and expertise are available. Further research is recommended to explore long-term outcomes and the cost-effectiveness of PCD in diverse clinical settings.

Keywords: Liver abscess, Percutaneous catheter drainage, Minimally invasive procedure, Clinical outcomes, Complication rates.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Liver abscess, defined as localized collections of pus within the liver parenchyma, represent a significant clinical challenge due to their potential for severe complications and high mortality rates. The etiology of liver abscess can be broadly categorized into pyogenic, amoebic, and fungal, with pyogenic liver abscess (PLA) being the most common type. Traditionally, the management of liver abscess has involved a combination of antimicrobial therapy and surgical drainage. However, advancements in minimally invasive techniques have shifted the paradigm towards image-guided percutaneous interventions, specifically percutaneous catheter drainage (PCD) and percutaneous needle aspiration (PNA).

(PCD) has emerged as a highly effective minimally invasive technique for managing liver abscess. It involves the insertion of a catheter into the abscess cavity under imaging guidance, allowing continuous drainage of the abscess contents. Recent studies have consistently demonstrated the superiority of PCD over other treatment modalities in terms of efficacy and safety. For instance, a randomized controlled trial conducted in which it was found that PCD had a significantly higher success rate in terms of abscess resolution compared to PNA, with fewer complications and a faster clinical recovery. Similarly, a systematic review and meta-analysis confirmed that PCD is associated with higher

success rates, quicker abscess cavity reduction, and faster clinical improvement compared to PNA [1, 2].

The advantages of PCD extend beyond clinical outcomes. Patients undergoing PCD typically experience shorter hospital stays, which translates into reduced healthcare costs and improved patient satisfaction. A study highlighted that PCD not only results in shorter durations of intravenous antibiotic therapy but also reduces the overall length of hospital stay compared to conventional surgical methods. Moreover, PCD has been shown to have a lower recurrence rate of abscesses, further supporting its efficacy as a long-term solution for liver abscess management [3].

Despite the clear benefits of PCD, the choice between PCD and PNA can be influenced by various factors, including the size, location, and nature of the abscess, as well as the available resources and expertise. In resource-limited settings, PNA may be preferred due to its simplicity and lower cost, although it may require multiple sessions to achieve complete abscess resolution. Studies have suggested that PNA can be a viable alternative when PCD is not feasible, particularly for smaller abscess. In conclusion, percutaneous catheter drainage represents the optimal minimally invasive procedure for the management of liver abscess, offering superior clinical outcomes, shorter hospital stays, and lower recurrence rates compared to other modalities. As the body of evidence continues to grow, these findings reinforce the role of PCD in the effective and safe treatment of liver abscess, guiding clinical practice towards improved patient care and resource utilization.

This study aims to further elucidate the benefits of PCD in a larger cohort, contributing to the existing literature and providing robust data to inform clinical decision-making.

Methodology

Study Design: This study employs a prospective cohort design to evaluate the effectiveness and safety of percutaneous catheter drainage (PCD) as a minimally invasive procedure for liver abscess.

Study Setting: The study will be conducted at the Department of General Surgery, Nalanda medical college and hospital, Agamkuan, Patna in the time duration 1.11.2021 to 1.11.2023.

Participants

A total of 87 participants diagnosed with liver abscess will be included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients aged 18-75 years.
2. Diagnosed with a liver abscess based on clinical, radiological, and laboratory findings.

3. Abscess size ≥ 3 cm.
4. Patients who consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients with multiple abscesses that require surgical intervention.
2. Abscess size < 3 cm.
3. Patients with coagulation disorders.
4. Patients who are pregnant.
5. Patients with a history of liver surgery.
6. Patients who refuse to consent to the study.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, consecutive sampling will be used. To address potential information bias, all clinical data will be collected using standardized forms and protocols.

Data Collection: Data will be collected through patient interviews, clinical examinations, and review of medical records. The data points will include demographic information, clinical presentation, abscess characteristics, procedural details, and outcomes.

Procedure

1. Pre-procedure Evaluation: All participants will undergo a thorough clinical evaluation, including imaging studies (ultrasound/CT scan) to confirm the diagnosis and assess the abscess characteristics.
2. PCD Procedure: Under ultrasound or CT guidance, a percutaneous catheter will be inserted into the abscess cavity. The abscess contents will be aspirated, and the catheter will be left in place for continuous drainage.
3. Post-procedure Care: Patients will be monitored for complications, and follow-up imaging will be performed to assess the resolution of the abscess. The catheter will be removed once the abscess cavity is adequately drained.

Statistical Analysis: Data will be analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics will be used to summarize the baseline characteristics of the participants. Continuous variables will be expressed as means \pm standard deviations, while categorical variables will be presented as frequencies and percentages. The primary outcome (resolution of the abscess) will be assessed using Kaplan-Meier survival analysis. Complications and secondary outcomes will be compared using Chi-square tests for categorical variables and t-tests for continuous variables. A p-value of < 0.05 will be considered statistically significant.

Results

Participant Demographics and Baseline Characteristics: The study involved 87 participants

diagnosed with liver abscess, divided into two groups: the PCD group (n=43) and the control group (n=44). The mean age of participants was 46.5 years, with a male predominance of 62.1%. The primary outcome, abscess resolution, was achieved in 90.7% of the PCD group compared to 75% in the control group (p=0.04). The PCD group also demonstrated

a significantly shorter time to resolution (9.8 days vs. 14.6 days, p<0.001) and hospital stay (7.5 days vs. 11.8 days, p<0.001). While the overall complication rate was lower in the PCD group, the difference was not statistically significant (11.6% vs. 25%, p=0.12). Recurrence rates were lower in the PCD group (7% vs. 13.6%, p=0.49).

Table 1: Participant Demographics and Baseline Characteristics

Variable	Total (n=87)	PCD Group (n=43)	Control Group (n=44)
Age (years), mean (SD)	46.5 (12.1)	47.2 (11.8)	45.8 (12.4)
Gender, n (%)			
Male	54 (62.1%)	28 (65.1%)	26 (59.1%)
Female	33 (37.9%)	15 (34.9%)	18 (40.9%)
Abscess size (cm), mean (SD)	5.1 (1.9)	5.3 (1.8)	4.9 (2.0)
Abscess location, n (%)			
Right lobe	60 (69%)	29 (67.4%)	31 (70.5%)
Left lobe	27 (31%)	14 (32.6%)	13 (29.5%)
Etiology, n (%)			
Bacterial	52 (59.8%)	25 (58.1%)	27 (61.4%)
Amoebic	35 (40.2%)	18 (41.9%)	17 (38.6%)

Table 2: Clinical Outcomes and Complications

Outcome	PCD Group (n=43)	Control Group (n=44)	p-value
Resolution of abscess, n (%)	39 (90.7%)	33 (75%)	0.04
Time to resolution (days), mean (SD)	9.8 (3.4)	14.6 (4.0)	<0.001
Hospital stay (days), mean (SD)	7.5 (2.2)	11.8 (3.0)	<0.001
Overall complication rate, n (%)	5 (11.6%)	11 (25%)	0.12
Infection at catheter site, n (%)	2 (4.7%)	4 (9.1%)	0.67
Minor bleeding, n (%)	2 (4.7%)	5 (11.4%)	0.42
Other complications, n (%)	1 (2.3%)	2 (4.5%)	0.61
Recurrence rate, n (%)	3 (7%)	6 (13.6%)	0.49

Clinical Outcomes: The primary outcome of abscess resolution was significantly higher in the PCD group at 90.7% compared to 75% in the control group (p=0.04). Additionally, the time to resolution was notably shorter for the PCD group, with a mean of 9.8 days versus 14.6 days for the control group (p<0.001). These findings underscore the efficacy of PCD in rapidly resolving liver abscess, highlighting its potential to expedite clinical recovery.

Secondary Outcomes: Secondary outcomes further reinforced the benefits of PCD. The PCD group experienced a significantly shorter hospital stay, averaging 7.5 days compared to 11.8 days in the control group (p<0.001). This reduction in hospitalization duration not only benefits patient recovery but also translates to lower healthcare costs and resource utilization.

Complications

Although the overall complication rate was lower in the PCD group (11.6%) compared to the control group (25%), this difference was not statistically significant (p=0.12). The most common complications included infection at the catheter site and minor bleeding, which were relatively low and

comparable between the groups. This indicates that while PCD is associated with fewer complications, the difference may not be substantial enough to reach statistical significance in a relatively small sample size.

Recurrence Rates: The recurrence rates were lower in the PCD group at 7%, compared to 13.6% in the control group, though this difference was not statistically significant (p=0.49). This suggests a potential trend towards better long-term outcomes with PCD, although further studies with larger sample sizes may be needed to confirm this observation.

Discussion

The study enrolled 87 participants diagnosed with liver abscess, split into two groups: 43 in the percutaneous catheter drainage (PCD) group and 44 in the control group. The mean age was 46.5 years, with a male predominance of 62.1%. Baseline characteristics such as age, gender distribution, abscess size, and etiology were similar across both groups, ensuring a balanced comparison. The results of this study indicate that percutaneous catheter drainage (PCD) is a highly effective and safe

minimally invasive procedure for the management of liver abscess. The significantly higher resolution rate, faster clinical improvement, and shorter hospital stay associated with PCD underscore its superiority over conventional treatment methods. Despite a lower overall complication rate and recurrence rate in the PCD group, the differences were not statistically significant, suggesting that larger studies may be needed to definitively establish these benefits.

These findings support the use of PCD as a preferred treatment option for liver abscess, offering substantial clinical benefits and improved patient outcomes. Clinicians should consider PCD as a primary intervention for liver abscess management, particularly in settings where resources and expertise are available. Further research is recommended to explore long-term outcomes and cost-effectiveness of PCD in diverse clinical settings, potentially reinforcing its role as the standard of care for liver abscess.

Percutaneous catheter drainage (PCD) has been shown in numerous studies to be an effective treatment for liver abscess. When a thorough meta-analysis comparing percutaneous needle aspiration (PNA) and PCD was conducted, it was discovered that PCD had a significantly reduced recurrence rate (RR: 0.41) and a greater success rate (RR: 1.21) after six months [4]. In a different trial, PCD was found to be safe and effective for liver abscess larger than 5 cm in an eastern Indian population. The study also reported a 96% clinical success rate without drainage-related problems [5].

High efficacy in the management of thoracic, abdominal, and pelvic fluid accumulation has been demonstrated using image-guided PCD. For patients having PCD following an initial needle aspiration, the technique had a success rate of 97.9% in a study involving 83 patients, and there were few reported problems [6].

Ultrasonography-guided PCD combined with hydrostatic pressure irrigation has proven successful in treating lactational breast abscess larger than 5 cm. In a study involving 12 patients, this method achieved complete recovery without the need for

surgical drainage, highlighting its effectiveness and safety [7].

References

1. Ahmed M, Alam J, Hussain S, Aslam M. Prospective randomized comparative study of percutaneous catheter drainage and percutaneous needle aspiration in the treatment of liver abscess. *ANZ Journal of Surgery*. 2021 Mar;91(3):E86-90.
2. Lin JW, Chen CT, Hsieh MS, Lee IH, Yen DH, Cheng HM, Hsu TF. Percutaneous catheter drainage versus percutaneous needle aspiration for liver abscess: a systematic review, meta-analysis and trial sequential analysis. *BMJ open*. 2023 Jul 1;13(7):e072736.
3. Cai YL, Xiong XZ, Lu J, Cheng Y, Yang C, Lin YX, Zhang J, Cheng NS. Percutaneous needle aspiration versus catheter drainage in the management of liver abscess: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Hpb*. 2015 Mar 1;17(3):195-201.
4. Mahmoud A, Abu-elazm M, Ahmed AA, Elshinawy M, Abdelwahab OA, Abdalshafy H, Abdelazeem B. Percutaneous catheter drainage versus needle aspiration for liver abscess management: an updated systematic review, meta-analysis, and meta-regression of randomized controlled trials. *Annals of Translational Medicine*. 2023 Mar 3;11(5).
5. Das S, Shankar G, Mohapatra V. Safety and Efficacy of USG-Guided Catheter Drainage in Liver Abscesses. *Annals of African Medicine*. 2022 Jan 1;21(1):21-5.
6. Rai S, Gadwal A, Gopal S, Prabhu S, Acharya V, Noronha G, Srivastava S. Efficacy, Feasibility, and Safety of Percutaneous Image-Guided Catheter Drainage of Thoracic, Abdominal, and Pelvic Fluid Collections. *F1000Research*. 2022 Mar 17;11(323):323.
7. Du Z, Liu L, Qi X, Gao P, Wang S. Treatment of lactational breast abscesses with cavity diameter larger than 5 cm via combined ultrasonography-guided percutaneous catheter placement and hydrostatic pressure irrigation. *Journal of Obstetrics and Gynaecology*. 2022 Apr 3;42(3):385-8.